

STATISTICAL STUDY OF POPULATION MIGRATION PROCESSES IN UZBEKISTAN

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Аннотация: Мақолада Ўзбекистонда миграцион жараёнларни статистик ўрганилиб, унда миграция салдоси, кўчиб келиш ва кўчиб кетишнинг динамикаси динамик таҳлил қилинган. Ушбу динамик таҳлиллар асосида миграцион жараёнлар тўғрисида фикр мулохазалар юритилиб, хулоса ва тавсиялар келтирилган.

Таянч сўзлар: миграцион жараёнлар, кўчиб келиш, кўчиб кетиш, механик ҳаракат, миграция салдоси, динамик таҳлил.

Аннотация: В статье статистически изучены миграционные процессы в Узбекистане, динамически проанализированы сальдо миграции, динамика иммиграции и миграции. На основе этих динамических анализов составляются мнения о миграционных процессах, даются выводы и рекомендации.

Ключевые слова: миграционные процессы, миграция, миграция, механическое движение, миграционный баланс, динамический анализ.

Abstract: In the article, the migration processes in Uzbekistan are statistically studied, the balance of migration, the dynamics of migration and migration are dynamically analyzed. On the basis of these dynamic analyses, opinions are made about migration processes, conclusions and recommendations are given .

Key words: migration processes , migration, migration, mechanical movement, migration balance, dynamic analysis.

INTRODUCTION

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, economic reforms aimed at ensuring macroeconomic stability and stable economic growth rates are being implemented consistently. Of course, the demographic situation of the country has a great role in this, and in the implementation of economic goals aimed at social interests, it is of great importance to study such aspects as the population, its growth, location, demographic structure from the perspective of the innovative development period of the economy. Because the population, both as the main productive force and as a consumer, is of decisive importance in the development of society. Today, the socio-economic development of our country is reaching a new level. At this stage, based on the objectives of the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan , ensuring stable and rapid economic growth in our country is the main issue of the national development strategy. Accordingly, in determining the current and future measures of the socio-economic development of our republic, it is necessary to take into account the influence of the demographic situation, to formulate economic development programs from the point of view of the impact of these processes, and to implement them consistently. In this regard, as

noted by the Honorable President Sh. Mirziyoev, "creating conditions for the full implementation of labor and entrepreneurial activity of the working-age population, improving the quality of the workforce, expanding the system of professional training, retraining and upgrading of skills of persons in need of work" [1] is considered an urgent issue. , its implementation is aimed at softening the demographic situation to a certain extent.

It is important to statistically study the impact of migration processes on the dynamics of the demographic situation in Uzbekistan. Migration processes also significantly affect the labor resources of the country. We believe that it is necessary to study the demographic situation of the population of Uzbekistan and its regions and to determine its specific characteristics, to analyze the migration processes of the population of Uzbekistan and its regions, and to summarize their results by choosing the methods of determining the growth trends and giving conclusions and making suggestions.

Review of literature on the subject

Foreign scientist Borisov V.A. by the scientific theoretical foundations of demography, information about the population, indicators of population dynamics, population composition and methods of its study, the demographic essence of birth, death, marriage and divorce, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the population, reproduction patterns, family structure, socio-economic status , population migration, demographic forecasting issues were studied [4].

In the studies of another group of foreign scientists, the formation of demography as a science, sources of studying demographic processes, information about the population, indicators of population dynamics, population composition and methods of its study, the demographic essence of birth, death, marriage and divorce, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the population, reproduction laws of division, gender, age, marriage and family composition, socio-economic status, population migration issues were studied [5].

Formation of demography as a science, sources of study of demographic processes, demographic essence of birth, death, marriage and divorce, quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the population, laws of reproduction, gender, age, marriage and family structure, socio-economic status, population migration, demographic forecasting issues Q.Kh. Researched by Abdurahmanov et al. [7].

Although the economic and statistical analysis of the demographic situation of the population has been theoretically studied in the above studies, until today, scientific studies on the impact of population migration processes on the dynamics of the demographic situation and the economic development of the country have not been carried out sufficiently.

Research methodology

Several research methodologies and methods were used in the preparation of the scientific article. In particular, methods such as scientific abstraction, expert assessment, induction and deduction, systematic analysis of socio-economic phenomena, economic-statistical analysis, comparative analysis, dynamic analysis are widely used.

Result and discussion

The diversity of population migration leads to different interpretations of the concept of population migration. To date, there are two approaches to the definition of migration , first : any form of territorial mobility of the population, regardless of permanent residence, purpose and duration . Secondly: it is understood that the place of residence is changed from a certain area to another area . As we know, we need to divide migration processes into two

parts. First: it is done by moving from one region to another region for permanent residence. Second: he moves to live temporarily. That is, he moves temporarily mainly for the purpose of work.

Migration processes can be divided into two main groups. The first is external migration and the second is internal migration. External migration is permanent or temporary migration from one country to another. In internal migration, permanent and temporary migrations are carried out within the country by regions. In our opinion, external and internal migration mainly involves the working-age population. Based on this, migration processes affect the demographic situation and economic processes.

Figure 1. Dynamics of migration indicators of the Republic of Uzbekistan, thousand people¹

If we statistically analyze migration processes in our country in recent years, we can see that the number of emigrants is greater than those who immigrated. In 2012, the number of immigrants made 169,701 people and was 5.7 per thousand. In 2021, this indicator was 256,814 people and 7.4 ppm. That is, we can see an increase of 1.7 ppm in 2021 compared to 2012. The number of emigrants in 2012 was 210,653 people and was 7.1 per cent. In 2021, this indicator was 275,079 people and 7.9 percent. That is, compared to 2012, it increased by 0.8 ppm in 2021[10].

Compared to 2021, the number of people who immigrated to our country in 2021 increased by 87,113 . The number of emigrants increased by 64,426 people. In 2012, the balance of migration was negative and amounted to -40,952 people. In 2021, this indicator was -18,265 people (Table 1).

Table 1

Dynamics of the number of immigrants to the Republic of Uzbekistan, people²

Years	of immigrants, people	Absolute additional growth, thousand people		Rate of increase or decrease, %		Additional growth (decrease) rate, %		Absolute value of 1% additional growth (decrease), thousand people	
		Basic method	Chain-like	Basic method	The chain is simon	Basic method	The chain is simon	Basic method	Chain method
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¹ www.stat.uz - Information of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

² www.stat.uz - Information of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the authors' calculations

A	1	2	3	4	5	6=4-100	7=5-100	8=3:7	9=1:100
2012	169 701	-	-	100	-	0.0	-	-	-
2013	155,084	-14 617	-14 617	91.4	91.4	-8.6	-8.6	1697.0	1550.8
2014	145 354	-24 347	-9 730	85.7	93.7	-14.3	-6.3	1550.8	1453.5
2015	139 280	-30 421	-6 074	82.1	95.8	-17.9	-4.2	1453.5	1392.8
2016	141 548	-28 153	2 268	83.4	101.6	-16.6	1.6	1392.8	1415.5
2017	157 149	-12 552	15 601	92.6	111.0	-7.4	11.0	1415.5	1571.5
2018	160 103	-9 598	2 954	94.3	101.9	-5.7	1.9	1571.5	1601.0
2019	158 861	-10,840	-1 242	93.6	99.2	-6.4	-0.8	1601.0	1588.6
2020	191 086	21 385	32 225	112.6	120.3	12.6	20.3	1588.6	1910.9
2021	256 814	87 113	65 728	151.3	134.4	51.3	34.4	1910.9	2568.1

In 2012, the number of immigrants to our country was 169,701, and in 2021, this figure was 256,814. We can see that the number of immigrants in 2021 increased by 87,113 people compared to 2012. In the period of 2012-2021, the lowest indicator was recorded in 2015, which decreased by 17.9 percent compared to 2012 (Table 1).

Table 2

Dynamics of the number of people who moved to the Republic of Uzbekistan, people³

Years	of emigrants, people	Absolute additional growth, thousand people		Rate of increase or decrease, %		Additional growth (decrease) rate, %		Absolute value of 1% additional growth (decrease), thousand people	
		Basic method	Chain-like	Basic method	The chain is simon	Basic method	The chain is simon	Basic method	Chain method
A	1	2	3	4	5	6=4-100	7=5-100	8=3:7	9=1:100
2012	210 653	-	-	100	-	0.0	-	-	-
2013	189 650	-21	-21	90.0	90.0	-10.0	-10.0	2106.5	1896.5

³ www.stat.uz - Information of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the authors' calculations.

		003	003						
2014	183 916	-26 737	-5 734	87.3	97.0	-12.7	-3.0	1896.5	1839.2
2015	168 579	- 42,074	-15 337	80.0	91.7	-20.0	-8.3	1839.2	1685.8
2016	167 796	-42 857	-783	79.7	99.5	-20.3	-0.5	1685.8	1678.0
2017	175 748	-34 905	7 952	83.4	104.7	-16.6	4.7	1678.0	1757.5
2018	174 832	- 35,821	-916	83.0	99.5	-17.0	-0.5	1757.5	1748.3
2019	169 547	-41 106	-5 285	80.5	97.0	-19.5	-3.0	1748.3	1695.5
2020	203 629	-7 024	34 082	96.7	120.1	-3.3	20.1	1695.5	2036.3
2021	275,079	64 426	71 450	130.6	135.1	30.6	35.1	2036.3	2750.8

In 2012, the number of people who immigrated from our country was 210,653, and in 2021, this indicator was 275,079 people. Compared to 2012, the number of immigrants in 2021 increased by 87,113 people. In the period between 2012-2021, the lowest indicator was 2016, and compared to 2012, it decreased by 20.3% in this year (Table 2).

Summary

The high level of labor migration among the able-bodied population, especially young men, and their long-term work in other countries are the reason for them to build a new family in this region. This situation remains a common cause of family conflicts, family breakdown, orphanhood and neglect. Also, migration creates distant relationships between spouses and increases the number of incomplete families and widows.

Migration causes the migration of skilled professionals and human resources, the spread of various diseases and the increase in the number of deaths, the growth of religious fanaticism, joining terrorist and extremist groups and movements. There is a tendency to lose language, religion, historical values, generational continuity and cultural heritage, affecting the prestige and prestige of the nation.

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